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TALK AROUND THINGS

PROTOTYPING AND DISCUSSION IN THE DESIGN PROCESS

Andreas Peter, Nicole Schadewitz, Peter Lloyd
The Design Group, The Open University, UK
andreas.peter@fhsg.ch, n.schadewitz@open.ac.uk, p.lloyd@open.ac.uk.

ABSTRACT

Designers have to manage an increasingly interdisciplinary process which requires extensive collaboration and thus discussion between different parties. One way to manage discussion is to use prototypes to get across ideas, a major component of design thinking. The primary purpose of this paper is to begin to bring together the areas of prototyping on the one hand, and studies of design discussion on the other hand. The paper reports two studies conducted at Swiss product design agencies. The first sought to apply existing typologies of prototyping to examples collected for a prototyping database. The second looked at the form and proportion of discussion in real-time design activity. The paper concludes by distinguishing between prototype-rich environments and prototype-poor environments suggesting an area for further work is to explore whether better quality discussion can be had in the former. This is important because, as the paper shows, discussion takes up a significant part of the design process.

Keywords: Prototyping, Discussion, Design Thinking

INTRODUCTION

Prototyping is considered a major component of design thinking (Brown, 2009; Cross, 2006; Lockwood, 2010) and evidence has shown that early prototyping in the design process results both in a better outcome (Yang & Epstein, 2005) and decreased design fixation (Youmans, 2011).

Typologies of prototyping, and the function that different kinds of prototypes perform have, however, received only limited attention, particularly in professional design practice. This is in contrast to the research area of sketching (arguably a form of prototyping) which has received considerable

attention (Ferguson, 1994; Goel, 1995, Rodgers et al., 2000). For example, Ferguson's (1994) typology of sketches being for "thinking, talking, and prescription" has been influential and led to further work (Van der Lugt, 2005). Additionally, studies such as Henderson (1999) have linked sketching activity with social function.

Typologies of prototyping do exist, however. Ullman (2003) lists four distinct types of prototyping: proof-of-concept, proof-of-product, proof-of-process, and proof-of-production while Sommerville (1995) identifies three types: throwaway prototypes, evolutionary prototypes, and incremental prototypes. Budde et al. (1992) identify a larger number of prototyping terms: evolutionary prototypes, experimental prototypes, presentation prototypes, prototypes proper, breadboard prototypes, and pilot system prototypes. Furthermore, Budde et al. identify two ways of prototype construction: horizontal prototyping (which builds a specific aspect or layer of a design solution) and vertical prototyping (which builds selected parts through all layers of a design solution).

Yang & Epstein (2005) propose categorising prototypes by the level of realism, or fidelity, of the prototypes, while Lim et al. (2008) propose a two dimensional framework for categorising prototypes: filtering (with the variables 'appearance', 'data', 'functionality', 'interactivity', and 'spatial structure'), and manifestation (with the variables 'material', 'resolution', and 'scope').

Significantly, little research relates the social function of prototypes - to enable discussion between different parties in the design process - with particular typologies. This is particularly noteworthy with the increasing complexity of products driving a need for interdisciplinary collaboration in design. Buchenau & Suri (2000), for example, emphasize that design products are more

about “holistic experiences set in context, rather than individual artifacts or components”.

Analyses of design discussions are a well-established field of research and Oak (2010) argues that in looking at design conversation researchers are able to observe “...how the micro activities of practice help to constitute the regularized circumstances of design practice and the concrete material environment.”

This paper begins to bring together the areas of prototyping and discussion in design. It does so by asking what kinds of prototypes are being used in design practice and what role they are playing within design-related conversations.

METHOD

The research described below was conducted in professional design contexts which made the application of an experimental method difficult. Indeed, one of the aims of the research was to develop new methods that were suited to observing designers in professional practice as they go about their everyday activity. Two studies of professional design practice were conducted.

The first study was at Studio Beat Karrer, a five-person design studio in Zurich producing interior design objects, for example furniture and light fittings. The different professions from which its employees come from reveal the studio's interdisciplinary approach: a business developer, a biochemist, and three industrial designers form its workforce. Over a period of months access was obtained to the studio. This began by conducting general interviews and led on to a more focused study of prototypes and observations of the design office environment. Data was collected in the form of a photographic database containing images of prototypes. A design meeting was also recorded.

The second study was of R.O.S.A., a design agency specialising in Interaction Design, and involved the collection and analysis of video data of real-time design activity streamed via a webcam at the agency's own initiative. As there was no audio feed with the webcam the focus of the study was on the ‘form’ of discussion, and the type of objects around which discussion took place, rather than the content.

Using a webcam to record professional design activity has only recently become a viable way of collecting data, so this approach represents a

genuinely new and innovative way of gaining access and insight into professional design activity. This method of data collection, using material that design practices are already broadcasting, represents a novel approach as it allows the collection of naturally-occurring data without interrupting the design process. Furthermore, the method reduces the problem of participant's bias, since they do not know that they are being observed. A short two and a half hour period of observation was decided upon to allow close observation and coding and allowing a realistic insight into a naturally occurring process.

RESULTS

PROTOTYPING IN THE DESIGN PROCESS

The results of the first study show both the importance that prototyping plays in the context of design practice, and the different ways that prototyping is used (figures 1a and 1b).

Figure 1a A 'function' prototype.

Figure 1b a 'style' prototype.

In interviews the designers at Studio Beat Karrer referred to their prototypes having “the power of the real” and being “playful and sensual”, themes echoed by Brown (2009). They drew a strong

distinction between ‘function’ prototypes (figure 1) and ‘style’ prototypes (figure 2).

Figure 2. Lounge design prototype

In practice, however, this distinction was difficult to discern. For example figures 2 and 3 show prototypes which, on the face of it, seem to be abstract studies in style yet, when one realises these are prototypes for a lounge design, it becomes clear that there are elements of function here too, the prototypes exploring structural features of the particular lounge arrangement.

Figure 3 Samples of different stitching techniques with lounge forms

Prototypes served a variety of different purposes in the design process: to show a specific functionality, to represent a shape or form, to test stability, to present a design solution to a client etc. These aspects can all converge in individual prototypes. The figures below show a few prototypes made for a hallstand. Figure 4 shows early functional prototypes made to test the shape’s stability.

Once a solution for the stability problem was found, a more refined model, incorporating solutions for other functional problems, such as the joining of the elements, but also representing stylistic solutions, was made using the actual material intended to be

used in production. This is shown in figure 5.

Figure 4. Functional prototypes made to test the stability of a hallstand design.

Although the designers made a clear distinction between function and style prototypes, as mentioned before, to the observer this is not so obvious; one sees more of an exploration of both things simultaneously.

Figure 5. Refined prototype incorporating different aspects of the design solution.

Figure 6. Style prototypes showing the aesthetic effects of different kinds of fabrics.

Prototypes, such as those shown in figure 6, are also used by the studio to reflect on different effects and appearances of materials. Figure 6 shows how the

type and colour of a fabric influences the overall appearance of a prototype chair; a play between the functional aspects of the design with the aesthetic effects, and the structural steel frame developing subtly as different materials were tried.

The interaction between prototypes and sketching is another interesting factor in the design process. Figure 7 illustrates examples of 'storing' sketches, that have developed from experiments using prototypes.

Figure 7. Idea board with storing sketches.

Many of the prototypes observed and photographed could be classified under typological headings mentioned in the introduction. For example the prototype extrusion for a lamp shown in figure 8 illustrates Yang's (2005) finding that a simpler design can lead to a more successful outcome. The prototype of the light fitting consists of only two parts and uses gills as cooling elements. This allows for a better heat distribution - thus a longer life of the LED's - as well as it giving the user implicit and tactile information about the ways in which the lamp operates.

8. A prototype for a light fitting using only two parts to achieve the desired design solution.

Similarly, the lighting prototype of Figure 9 is an

example of Ullman's 'proof-of-production' prototype category. In an interview, one designer pointed out their importance: "When the building of the prototype is a tedious and difficult work, chances are that the production of the final product will be too."

Figure 9. Proof-of-production prototype.

The prototypes mentioned above fit most closely with Ullman's (2003) typology: proof-of-concept, proof-of-product, proof-of-process, and proof-of-production. Within the design process of Studio Beat Karrer, the use of different kinds of prototypes is emphasized in individual development stages but not restricted to them exclusively. The process and structure of the workflow at the agency is usually defined upfront in every project. The main phases split into:

- initial research about the problem;
- briefing with the client;
- deepening of the research;
- problem definition;
- refinement of the prototypes.

Sketching and prototyping are used from the very beginning of this process. Figure 10 shows an early 'thinking sketch', with figure 11 showing an early prototype for chair.

According to the head of the agency the preference is to move very early to prototyping and to experiment widely with different materials. CAD is only used late in the development process, mostly for representational purposes or to test a specific layout.

One designer, talking about the tacit knowledge that prototypes embody, explained that a need for physical embodiment is evident throughout the studio's workshop, desks and conference room (see

figures 13 and 14).

Much thought is given to the form of the prototypes being discussed, especially when presenting to a client and having a prototype-rich environment upon which to draw in conducting discussions is extremely advantageous.

Figure 10. Early thinking sketches.

Occasionally the design team deliberately presents a rough prototype to a client to set the focus of the conversation and to leave space for imaginative discussion and interpretation. At other times a refined prototype, set within its context of use, is shown to communicate a final design solution more

precisely. What this shows is that prototypes can be used effectively to set the frame of discussions with clients, the designers judging in advance the kind of discussions they want to have in order to solicit the information they need to develop the design further.

Figure 11. Early, quick and dirty prototype.

DISCUSSION IN THE DESIGN PROCESS

After repeated viewings of the webcam video for study 2, obtained from a website feed at the agency's own initiative, we decided to turn the lack of audio to our advantage and analyse the form of the design activity we observed. This was done by looking at the proportion of time spent in activity

Figure 12. Observational study using a live-streaming webcam. The four images reveal different types of discussion taking place, and in different parts of the space. Overall, however, this environment was classified as 'prototype-poor'.

that could be obviously classified as ‘discussion’ during the entire two and a half hour period that the observation was carried out. Figure 12 shows screenshots where four different types of discussion activity can be observed. Table 1 shows the classification and results obtained.

Type of Discussion	Duration	Proportion of time
Between two people in front of computer screen	27 min 15 secs	18.3%
Between three people in front of computer screen	2 min 32 secs	1.7%
Between two people from their desks	19 min 30 secs	13.1%
between three people from their desks	6 min 40 secs	4.5%
between two people at one desk	3 min 28 secs	2.3%
No discussion	1 hour 29 min	60.1%
Total Observation Time	2 hour 28 min	100%

Table 1. Different forms of discussion observed.

The form and frequency of the discussion might be seen as an indication of the different roles each person performs in the office. The designer at the desk in the front of the frame appears to hold some sort of supervising function as the two co-workers at the back address him regularly, while they do not seem to discuss anything amongst themselves. The meetings take place at individual workstations, or as occasional discussion from their desks, indicating an informal nature to conversations. While the two designers at the back of the office were using their keyboards quite regularly, the ‘supervisor’ in the front hardly did so at all, further reinforcing his role as a manager.

As their screens did not reveal what the individual designers were working on, it is difficult to know what their discussions were actually based on. Due to the services offered by the company, it is safe to say that it involved some sort of web-based interface design. We make the assumption that any activity taking part in a professional design practice constitutes part of a design process since work, in a general and self-evident sense, is being done.

The general form of the conversation - the two designers regularly addressing the ‘supervisor’, who then went to their desks - make it seem as if the designers were asking for feedback and guidance regarding their work. On the other hand, the few occasions where the designers joined the ‘supervisor’ at his desk, the gestures seemed to indicate that

some sort of reference or example was shown to them. While it may not be obvious what was being developed, Table 1 shows that the designers spent more than 1/3 of their time discussing their work.

The designers spent about the same amount of time casually discussing from their desks and more formally discussing the work of an individual designer at his computer screen. It was surprising in some respects that the frequency of discussion was so high. Especially so as the discussions occurred as many, spontaneous and brief conversations, instead of single, long meetings. Whether this was due to the kind of work being accomplished during the observational period, the specific corporate culture at the design agency, or some other reason could not be discerned.

Figure 13. Stand-up table for informal meetings, and example of a ‘prototype-rich’ environment.

The type of discussion observed at R.O.S.A. was compared with that at Studio Beat Karrer and there are certain similarities. Many conversations are carried out in a very informal manner, with a cup of coffee in the kitchen, or at desks and these kind of discussions take place frequently and casually. Most group discussions at Beat Karrer, however, took place in the kitchen/workshop area shown in figure 13. More formal discussions with clients were held in the main conference room, shown in Figure 14, with a more serene atmosphere, though still with plenty of prototypes.

While the conference room allows for a more focused discussion of selected prototypes, the stand-up table of figure 13, as part of the workshop, seemed to open up the conversation in a more playful manner. A lot of inspiring material and current work is lying around the workspace and seemed to provoke easy ways to switch topics of discussion.

What was striking between the two studies was the

difference in the number of prototypes. At Studio Beat Karrer prototypes of design activity were strewn everywhere, and seemed a constant source of discussion. Figures 15 and 16 show two examples of discussions occurring over prototypes.

Figure 14. Conference room for formal meetings.

This was completely different to the environment at R.O.S.A. Figure 13 clearly shows a prototype-rich environment which compares markedly with Figure 11, a relatively prototype-poor environment.

Figure 15. Designers discussing functional properties on a style prototype.

Another noticeable observation is the ‘focussing’ nature of prototype discussions. In figure 16, for example, the focus of the two people in discussion clearly converges on the prototype.

Figure 16. Designers discussing aesthetic consequences on a function prototype.

While explaining their ideas and insights to each other and trying to gain common ground, the designers used a variety of different tools such as talking sketches - shown in Figure 17 - functional and style prototypes, as well as other material related to the prototypes, such as a documentation of the design research and presentational brochures.

Figure 17. Using talking sketches during conversation to gain common ground.

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The research in this paper identified many of the ‘types’ of prototypes identified in previous work, but particularly the typologies of Ullman (2003), Sommerville (1995), and Budde et al. (1992). The study also supports Oak’s (2010) claim that communication and negotiation are central to design, and confirms her observation that design practice is deeply discursive and contextually-specific.

We observed different kinds of discussion in design practice, ranging from formal to occasional conversations. The distinction between prototyping-rich and prototyping-poor environments provides a good basis on which to build in this respect. One thing that was mentioned by the designers at Beat Karrer was that prototypes enable discussion about embodied design issues, sometimes referred to as tacit knowledge, an often overlooked feature of the design process in professional practice.

Although the focus of these initial studies were narrow, we were able to gather and analyze different kinds of data directly from professional design practice, something that is rare in design research. The innovative method of using a webcam broadcast to collect naturally occurring data from professional practice also proved successful.

The data gathered in the two case studies reveals two important aspects of the design process - prototyping and discussion - and future work will

break these activities down further exploring in detail how prototyping and discussion are related in a number of different design environments.

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